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Impact of Mobility Models on Multi-Path Routing in Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

The high-level contribution of this paper is a detailed simulation based analysis about the impact of mobility models on the performance of node-disjoint and link-disjoint multi-path routing algorithms for mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs). We consider the following MANET mobility models: Random Waypoint, Random Direction, Gauss-Markov, City Section and Manhattan mobility models. Simulations have been conducted for various network density and node mobility levels. The performance metrics studied include the lifetime per multi-path set, the multi-path set size and the average hop count per multi-path. For almost every simulation condition, we observe the Gauss-Markov mobility model to yield the least number of multi-paths, but the lifetime per multi-path set under this mobility model is the maximum. The Random Direction mobility model yields the smallest lifetime per multi-path set, even though it yields a relatively larger number of multi-paths.

KEYWORDS

Mobility Models, Multi-path Routing, Simulations, Mobile Ad hoc Networks

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Trust Based Clustering and Secure Routing Scheme for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a distributed self-organizing trust based clustering framework for securing ad hoc networks. The mobile nodes are vulnerable to security attacks, so ensuring the security of the network is essential. To enhance security, it is important to evaluate the trustworthiness of nodes without depending on central authorities. In our proposal the evidence of trustworthiness is captured in an efficient manner and from broader perspectives including direct interactions with neighbors, observing interactions of neighbors and through recommendations. Our prediction scheme uses a trust evaluation algorithm at each node to calculate the direct trust rating normalized as a fuzzy value between zero and one. The evidence theory of Dempster-Shafer [7], [8] used in order to combine the evidences collected by a clusterhead itself and the recommendations from other neighbor nodes. Moreover, in our scheme we do not restrict to a single gateway node for inter cluster routing.

Keywords:

Ad hoc networks, Trust, Cluster, Security, Distributed Leader Election

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A Proactive Load-Aware Gateway Discovery in Ad Hoc Networks for Internet Connectivity

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ABSTRACT

When a Mobile Ad Hoc network (MANET) is connected to the Internet, it is important for mobile nodes to detect available Internet gateway (IGW) providing access to the Internet. Gateway discovery time have strong influence on packet delay and throughput. In most of the cases, a mobile node uses min- hops to the gateway to communicate a fixed host connected to an Internet. However, a minimum hop path may not always be efficient if some nodes along the path have longer interface queue of waiting packets. Thus, the focus of the paper is to first analyse existing load-aware routing protocols in MANET and then based on this analysis, devise a proactive load-aware gateway discovery scheme that takes in to account size of interface queue in addition to the traditional min hop metric. This approach also allows an efficient handoff from one Internet gateway to another Internet gateway and still maintains a seamless connectivity to a fixed host. We examine the impact of traffic load and node mobility in terms of two metrics: throughput and average end-to-end delay to assess the performance of the proposed protocol. Simulation results indicate that our protocol outperforms existing solution.

KEYWORDS

MANET, Internet Gateway Discovery, Load Balancing, Congestion, Mobile IP, Internet, AODV, NS2, Performance Evaluation.

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Performance Analysis of the Routing Protocols for Video Streaming Over Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs) are very considered attractive for many applications. Routing protocol is considered as the most important element of MANET. However, Media streaming over MANET is a quite demanding task. In this paper the performances of MANET routing protocols have been investigated for video applications. Some popular routing protocols namely Dynamic Source Routing (DSR) Ad hoc On-demand Distance Vector (AODV), Temporally-Ordered Routing Algorithm (TORA), Optimized Link State Routing Protocol (OLSR), and Geographic Routing Protocol (GRP) have been considered in this paper. A comparative performance analysis of these routing protocols has been presented in this paper for supporting video streaming applications.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Ad hoc Networks, routing protocols, video streaming, DSR, AODV, TORA, OSLR, GRP, QoS.

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Mobile Ad-Hoc Network Based Relaying Data System for Oceanic Flight Routes in Aeronautical Communications

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a reliable system to overcome the weakness of current the HF radio communication system for oceanic aeronautical flight routes. This system uses only one aeronautical VHF channel with air-to-air radio relay system based on local mobile Ad-hoc networks. For access to/from all aircrafts in the system, a TDMA (Time Division Multiple Access) scheme is proposed to be used where each aircraft is assigned one time slot during its presence in the system in order to transmit its own packet by itself or relay them using neighbouring aircrafts. These packets contain aircraft position, ID, relative direction which are used to build a routing table at each aircraft. In addition, several algorithms for relaying packets; schemes to reduce the packet-loss-ratio as well as to reduce the interference caused by surrounding aircrafts have been proposed. The simulations have shown the improvement of such proposals when examining system performance under real air-traffic scenarios. This system strengthens the reliability of oceanic aeronautical communication and increases situational awareness of all oceanic flights as an effective solution to operate more flights on the ocean but in higher safety.

KEYWORDS

Oceanic air traffic control communications, air-to-air communication, air-to-ground, mobile Ad-hoc networks

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Performance Comparison of Mobile Ad Hoc Network Routing Protocols

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ABSTRACT

Mobile Ad-hoc Network (MANET) is an infrastructure less and decentralized network which need a robust dynamic routing protocol. Many routing protocols for such networks have been proposed so far to find optimized routes from source to the destination and prominent among them are Dynamic Source Routing (DSR), Ad-hoc On Demand Distance Vector (AODV), and Destination-Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV) routing protocols. The performance comparison of these protocols should be considered as the primary step towards the invention of a new routing protocol. This paper presents a performance comparison of proactive and reactive routing protocols DSDV, AODV and DSR based on QoS metrics (packet delivery ratio, average end-to-end delay, throughput, jitter), normalized routing overhead and normalized MAC overhead by using the NS-2 simulator. The performance comparison is conducted by varying mobility speed, number of nodes and data rate. The comparison results show that AODV performs optimally well not the best among all the studied protocols.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Ad hoc Network (MANET), AODV, DSDV, DSR

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An Efficient Cluster Based Approach for Multi-Source Multicast Routing Protocol in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

Mobile ad hoc networks are becoming an important concept of modern communication technologies and services. It provides some advantages to this communication world such as self-organizing and decentralization. In this paper, we are going to design a cluster-based multi source multicast routing protocol with new cluster head election, path construction and maintenance techniques. The main objective of this work to compute the maximum performance of proposed routing protocol in various environments, and also it has been compared with Multicast Ad-hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (MAODV) and On-Demand Multicast Routing Protocol (ODMRP) to prove the performance of delivery ratio, control overhead and forwarding efficiency.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Ad hoc Networks, Routing Protocols, MAODV, ODMRP, Multicasting, Clustering, Network Simulator

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A QoS Routing Protocol Based on Available Bandwidth Estimation for Wireless Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

At the same time as the emergence of multimedia in mobile Ad hoc networks, research for the introduction of the quality of service (QoS) has received much attention. However, when designing a QoS solution, the estimation of the available resources still represents one of the main issues. This paper suggests an approach to estimate available resources on a node. This approach is based on the estimation of the busy ratio of the shared canal. We consider in our estimation the several constraints related to the Ad hoc transmission mode such as Interference phenomena. This approach is implemented on the AODV routing protocol. We call AODVwithQoS our new routing protocol. We also performed a performance evaluation by simulations using NS2 simulator. The results confirm that AODVwithQoS provides QoS support in ad hoc wireless networks with good performance and low overhead.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Ad hoc networks, QoS, Available resources, Estimation, Constraints, Shared canal, Interference phenomena.

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CR-MAC: A Multichannel MAC Protocol for Cognitive Radio AD HOC Networks

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a cross-layer based cognitive radio multichannel medium access control (MAC) protocol with TDMA, which integrate the spectrum sensing at physical (PHY) layer and the packet scheduling at MAC layer, for the ad hoc wireless networks. The IEEE 802.11 standard allows for the use of multiple channels available at the PHY layer, but its MAC protocol is designed only for a single channel. A single channel MAC protocol does not work well in a multichannel environment, because of the multichannel hidden terminal problem. Our proposed protocol enables secondary users (SUs) to utilize multiple channels by switching channels dynamically, thus increasing network throughput. In our proposed protocol, each SU is equipped with only one spectrum agile transceiver, but solves the multichannel hidden terminal problem using temporal synchronization. The proposed cognitive radio MAC (CR-MAC) protocol allows SUs to identify and use the unused frequency spectrum in a way that constrains the level of interference to the primary users (PUs). Our scheme improves network throughput significantly, especially when the network is highly congested. The simulation results show that our proposed CR-MAC protocol successfully exploits multiple channels and significantly improves network performance by using the licensed spectrum band opportunistically and protects PUs from interference, even in hidden terminal situations.

KEYWORDS

Cognitive radio, multichannel MAC, ad hoc networks, frequency spectrum, TDMA, channel sensing.

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Secure Routing and Data Transmission in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present an identity (ID) based protocol that secures AODV and TCP so that it can be used in dynamic and attack prone environments of mobile ad hoc networks. The proposed protocol protects AODV using Sequential Aggregate Signatures (SAS) based on RSA. It also generates a session key for each pair of source-destination nodes of a MANET for securing the end-to-end transmitted data. Here each node has an ID which is evaluated from its public key and the messages that are sent are authenticated with a signature/ MAC. The proposed scheme does not allow a node to change its ID throughout the network lifetime. Thus it makes the network secure against attacks that target AODV and TCP in MANET. We present performance analysis to validate our claim.

INDEX TERMS

MANET, AODV, TCP, Signature, Attacker, Security

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